

Comparative Durability of Small GFRP and Steel RC Columns in a Simulate Marine Environment

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a comparative durability study on Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) and steel-reinforced concrete (RC) columns in a simulated marine environment. The aim was to assess the impact of wet/dry cycles of exposure on GFRP rebar durability, in conditions promoting rebar corrosion. Specimens included RC columns, and GFRP and steel coupons. Bar tests demonstrated GFRP's superior durability compared to steel after 52 weeks of exposure while conditioning time had pronounced adverse effects on the load-deformation behaviour of column specimens. Both GFRP and steel-reinforced columns showed similar reductions in load capacities. GFRP-reinforced columns indicated only a small reduction in ductility, measured as the ratio of axial strains corresponding to the second peak and the peak peak. However, a substantial decrease in ductility for steel-reinforced columns was observed.

KEYWORDS

GFRP, Steel, Reinforced Columns, Durability; Comparative Study; Marine Environment.

INTRODUCTION

The use of glass fiber reinforced polymers (GFRP) bars as internal reinforcement in reinforced concrete (RC) members is gaining acceptance in modern RC construction, following decades of research into this novel reinforcement. It is well known that GFRP rebars have high tensile strength, high strength-to-weight ratio, low electrical conductivity, are non-magnetic and more importantly, are non-corrosive. Manufacturers have developed reliable and consistent products that can be used in construction projects where the durability requirements of RC are high. Specifically, RC elements in zones that promote corrosion such as coastal infrastructure, mining tunnels, transportation and bridge infrastructure can be constructed with GFRP bars as an alternative to steel rebar, which corrodes in response to chloride ion ingress after multiple cycles of exposure. In North America, this is a prevalent problem in tidal zones and highway bridges/overpasses, where the constant wetting and drying of steel RC infrastructure from saline solution or seawater degrades the elements to levels of instability and danger to the public. To that end, research is underway regarding the durability of GFRP bars as a stand-alone material in different corrosive environments, to understand potential durability problems with GFRP and mitigate another 50–100-year cycle of infrastructure repair.

The durability of GFRP bars exposed to simulated or real marine conditions has been investigated by many researchers such as Robert & Benmokrane 2013; Tu et al. 2020; El-Hassan et al. 2017, 2018; Wang et al. 2017, 2018; Almusallam et al. 2012; Chen et al. 2007; Jia et al. 2019; Morales et al. 2021; and Ruiz Empananza et al. 2022. These studies primarily investigated the degradation of tensile strength and elastic modulus of FRP bars after constant immersion into varying saline-type solutions at different temperatures. Based on feasibility and availability, the authors adopted various solutions: 3.5% NaCl (Robert and Benmokrane 2013; Wang et al. 2017, 2018); 3% NaCl with 0.5% NaSO₄ (Chen et al. 2007; Jia et al. 2019); simulated seawater (Tu et al. 2020); or some local coastal fresh seawater (Morales et al. 2021; Ruiz Empananza et al. 2022).

The solutions used in these tests were prepared—either following molecular chemistry (NaCl, NaSO₄) or ASTM D1141 standard for simulating seawater (ASTM 2013)—to achieve a salinity of 3.5% or 35 parts per thousand (PPT), which is typical for seawater. Seawater with 35 PPT salinity contains

approximately 19.8 PPT Cl, 11 PPT Na, 2.8 PPT SO₄, 1.3 PPT Mg, 0.4 PPT K, and 0.4 PPT Ca. Therefore, it may be oversimplified to include only a few major salts when investigating the durability of GFRP rebar and RC in a simulated marine environment. Nonetheless, there is a consensus that tensile strength degradation is observed irrespective of the type of saline solution used. Robert and Benomkrane (2013) observed tensile strength retentions (TSR) of up to 86% of ambient strengths after 12 months of immersion at 50°C. Wang et al. (2017) observed reductions of 87.4% and 60.2% after 63 days of exposure at temperatures of 32 °C and 55 °C, respectively. Likewise, Chen et al. (2007) observed a TSR of 74% after 70 days of conditioning at 60°C. Under real marine seawater accelerated conditions (Ruiz Emparanza 2022) at 60°C, TSRs of 83% to 45% for rebars of different manufacturers were observed. In general, no significant changes in tensile modulus were observed in these studies. All of these studies were done on bare GFRP bars, and it is important to note that the test results of bare GFRP bar specimens do not necessarily represent the actual field conditions.

To obtain a more accurate representation of real-world conditions, additional experiments have been reported investigating specific variables related to GFRP-RC members. These experiments focussed on (1) embedding the GFRP bar in concrete prisms, (2) subjecting the bars to sustained loads or (3) a combination of both variables. These conditions more closely represent actual field conditions. For GFRP bars embedded in concrete prisms and conditioned at 60°C, TSRs of 61% after 120 days and 63.9% after 220 days were reported by Jia et al. (2019) and Li et al. (2020), respectively. Under real seawater solutions at 60°C, TSRs of 71% after 15 months, 84% after 18 months and 74% to 69% after 24 months were observed by El-Hassan et al. (2017), Almusallam et al. (2012) and Morales et al. (2021), respectively. When subjected to sustained loads, similar ranges of strength retentions, around 68%-96%, were observed for equivalent conditioning temperatures and durations, with sustained loads up to 40% (Tu et al. 2020; El-Hassan et al. 2018; Wang et al. 2018). While these results show that GFRP degrades under fully immersed conditions, these environments still do not fully represent actual corrosive conditions that involve other varying conditions such as wet/dry cycles.

Corrosion of steel is an electrochemical process which involves the flow of charges (electrons and ions) between the steel rebar and concrete. Subsequently, the ferrous ions (Fe²⁺) from the steel bar combine with hydroxide ions (OH⁻) in concrete to form iron hydroxide [Fe(OH)₂] or rust at the interface. This process of steel corrosion gets expedited when exposed to continuous salts, increased temperatures, and oxygen. Therefore, researchers adopted the approach of wet/dry cycles under certain increased temperatures to simulate the worst field conditions. A limited amount of research, which tried to replicate the marine environment through wet/dry cycles, has also been reported.

Chen et al. (2007) reported a TSR of 86% after 9 cycles of 8 days at 50°C, while Almusallam et al. (2012) reported a TSR of 91% after unknown cycles duration and lengths at 50°C with rebar embedded in concrete prisms. Furthermore, GFRP laminates subjected to wet/dry conditions and sustained loads up to 40% experienced a TSR of 79% after 24-hour cycles for 260 days at ambient temperatures (Li et al. 2017). These results indicate that GFRP bars are prone to degradation under marine conditions; however, no overarching study has been reported in the literature, particularly to investigate the impact of marine conditions on GFRP-RC members.

Elhamaymy et al. (2020, 2021) tested square and circular GFRP-RC columns under compression after 12 months of continuous immersion into 3.5% NaCl saline solution at a temperature of 60°C. Any degradation in GFRP rebar properties due to this conditioning could not be investigated because column response was governed by a 20%-26% increase in concrete compressive strength due to continuous hydration. Elhamaymy et al. (2022) pre-conditioned rectilinear ties and straight GFRP bars in 3.5% NaCl saline solution at temperatures of 22°C, 40°C and 60°C for 12 months. GFRP RC columns were then assembled and tested in compression. Columns whose GFRP bars were preconditioned at 40°C and 60 °C showed post-peak strength enhancement of 6.5% and 14%, respectively compared to columns with unconditioned GFRP bars. Furthermore, GFRP bars preconditioned at 60 °C showed a TSR of 84% and 90% for No.5 and No.6 bars, respectively, when compared with bar strengths preconditioned at 22°C.

In summary, the existing experimental literature reveals a lack of comprehensive understanding regarding the durability of GFRP-RC members. To address this gap, research undertaken at the University of Toronto aims to bridge this knowledge gap through a comparative methodology. The investigation involves subjecting GFRP-RC and steel-RC columns to wet/dry cycles, simulated seawater exposure, and elevated temperatures to assess their durability. This paper presents findings from the early stages of this study.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The experimental program follows a methodology, where equivalently designed steel and GFRP RC columns were constructed and conditioned in a simulated marine environment via wet/dry cycles and accelerated with heat. The program aims to observe the potential strength degradation in the material properties of the reinforcement, column strength, and column ductility. While 305 mm diameter and 1258 mm long columns were also included in this test program, results from the only four column specimens with dimensions of 203 mm in diameter and 813 mm in height, are presented here due to the limited available space. Of the four, two columns were conditioned for 52 weeks (wet/dry protocol) and the other two were kept under ambient conditions for the same duration. Each exposure type contained one column exclusively reinforced with steel and another column exclusively reinforced with GFRP rebar. Additionally, steel and GFRP rebar coupons were conditioned for periods of 17, 34 and 52 weeks, and then tested under tension for material characterization. The following sections provide detailed information on the materials used, specimens' details and conditioning/testing protocol.

Material Characteristics

GFRP Bars

The GFRP reinforcing bars used for this study were manufactured by the pultrusion process and are comprised of E-Glass fibers and vinyl-ester resin. The bars are all sand coated, with a more typical finer/loose sand coat for longitudinal straight bars and a coarser/tougher sand coat for spirals. The manufacturer specifications and lab-tested ambient/virgin tensile results are presented in Table 1. The tests were carried out on straight bars or straight portions of bent bars (#2 bars). All GFRP rebar material characterization tests were carried out in accordance with ASTM D7205/D7205M-06 and Annex C of CSA S806-12 (ASTM 2016; CSA 2017).

Table 1: GFRP Reinforcement Specification and Ambient Mechanical Properties

Bar Size	Manufacturers' Quality Control Specs				Lab Tested Tensile Properties ¹						
	A [mm ²]	d [mm]	V _f [%]	T _g [°C]	n	Stress		Modulus		Ultimate Strain	
						f _u [MPa]	COV [%]	E [MPa]	COV [%]	ε _u [μm/km]	COV [%]
#2	41	7.2	75.4	116	5	770.2	2.9	39380	2.7	19561	2.2
#4	124	12.6	83.5	107	5	1018.7	2.5	51974	1.7	19600	1.6

¹Based on Manufacturers QC Area – Subjected to Change; A = Bar Area; d = Bar Diameter; V_f = Fiber Content; T_g = Glass Transition Temperature; f_u = Ultimate Stress; E = Elastic Modulus; ε_u = Rupture Strain, Calculated as f_u/E

Steel Bars

The steel bars used in the program were sourced to have an equivalent cross-sectional area to that of the GFRP reinforcement. To that end, US#4 bar and D6 deformed wire were used for the longitudinal and spiral reinforcement with ratios to their GFRP counterparts of 0.91 and 1.04, respectively. Table 2 presents the ambient test results. All steel bar material characterization tests were done in accordance with ASTM A370-20 (ASTM 2020).

Table 2: Steel Reinforcement Specification and Ambient Mechanical Properties

Bar Size	Type	A [mm ²]	n	Yield Stress		Ultimate Stress		Youngs Modulus	
				f _y [MPa]	COV [%]	f _u [MPa]	COV [%]	E [MPa]	COV [%]
D6	Cold-Formed ¹	37.4	3	579.1	1.4	593.9	0.1	201390	5.9
US#4	Hot-Formed	129.0	3	448.7	3.6	718.3	0.9	207740	2.9

¹Cold-Formed yield point calculated using 0.2% offset method; A = Bar Area; f_y = Yield Stress; f_u = Ultimate Stress; E = Elastic Modulus

Concrete

The concrete used in the current program was cast with a 120-130 mm slump. Cylinder preparation and testing for uniaxial concrete properties were done in accordance with ASTM C192/C192M – 19 & C39/C39M-21 standards. The 28-day strength was 25.4 MPa. Cylinders with a diameter of 6 inches (152 mm) were used for uniaxial concrete compression tests for up to 21 days, while 4 inches cylinders were used for tests conducted at 28 days and beyond. Table 3 presents the relevant concrete material properties at different ages for both ambient and wet/dry conditioned cylinders.

Table 3: Concrete Cylinder Mechanical Properties

Age [Days]	Exposure Type	n	Stress		Modulus		Strain	
			f' _c [MPa]	COV [%]	E _c [MPa]	COV [%]	ε' _c [mm/mm]	COV [%]
28	Ambient	3	25.4	7.7	12142	0.113	0.0025	1.5
523/558 ¹	Ambient	6	29.7	7.0	24038	0.088	0.0021	5.9
523/558 ¹	Conditioned	6	36.8	6.6	31194	0.085	0.0018	5.8

¹Properties taken as the average of both ages; f'_c = Uniaxial Compressive Strength; E_c = Initial Concrete Stiffness; ε'_c = Peak Compressive Strain

Specimen Details & Preparation

The column specimens for both groups (steel and GFRP) were designed to have approximately equivalent reinforcement areas, the same longitudinal/transverse reinforcement ratios, and the same gross dimensioning. This would assure that the diffusion and wet/drying process would be similar for both types of specimens during conditioning. The clear cover for all 203 x 813 mm columns was 13 mm. The column cages and design detail are presented in Figure 1. The gross dimensions, column reinforcement detailing, and column testing variables are presented in Table 4. The nomenclature for the columns is as follows: AB_C_D where A is the size, either small (S) or large (L); B is the reinforcement type, either steel (S) or GFRP (G); C is the exposure types, either ambient (A) or conditioned (C); and D is the time of exposure in weeks. For example, SG_C_52 is a small (203 mm diameter) GFRP RC column specimen conditioned for 52 weeks. Upon curing after 28 days, the columns were subjected to wet/dry conditioning cycles in the accelerated simulated marine environment. After the conditioning of the columns, the ends of the columns were wrapped with carbon FRP sheets (CFRP) to ensure that the failure would occur in the instrumented test zone and not at the ends (Figure 1d).

Table 4: Column Matrix and Specimen Details

ID	Reinf.	Exposure/Time [Weeks]	d [mm]	H [mm]	Long. Reinf	Spiral Reinf.	ρ _l [%]	ρ _{lt} [%]
SG_A_52	GFRP	A/52	203	813	5 #4	#2 @ 55mm	1.9	1.8
SG_C_52		C/52						
SS_A_52	Steel	A/52			5 US#4	D6 @ 55mm	2.0	1.7
SS_C_52		C/52						

Long. = Longitudinal; Reinf. = Reinforcement; ρ_l = long. reinforcement ratio; ρ_{lt} = transverse reinforcement ratio;

Figure 1: Specimens' Design Details and Instrumentation

The coupon specimens were conditioned by assembling them into timber support to allow for uniform diffusion around the bars. Only 80% of the free length of the bars was exposed to the solution, either as bars alone or bar embedded in prisms. The ends were wrapped with tape to preserve the structural integrity of the anchors for testing under tension (Figure 1c). After 17, 34 and 52 weeks of conditioning, #2 GFRP, #4 GFRP, D6 steel and d14 steel bars were selected for tensile testing.

Testing Protocols

Environmental Conditioning Protocols

The conditions for accelerated aging and conditioning plan were selected based on what would best represent a lab-induced marine environment. To that end, the accelerated simulated marine environment was simulated using wet/dry cycles lasting one week each. Each cycle consisted of 3 days (72 hours) submerged in the simulated seawater solution at elevated temperatures, followed by 3 days (72 hours) of ambient drying and one 24-hour period of dry heating, where the specimens were brought back up to temperature for the re-introduction of heated simulated seawater solution. The immersion solution was heated to accelerate the aging process of the specimens, as identified in ASTM C1560-03 (ASTM 2016). The average temperature for the 3 wetting days was $53-54^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.3-0.4^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $30-31^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 12-13^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the 4 days of drying. The simulated seawater of 35 PPT salinity was prepared in accordance with ASTM D1141-98. Samples of the solution were taken 3 times a week, and the Ph was adjusted to 8.2 on a weekly basis while the solution salinity was refreshed on a bi-weekly or monthly basis by re-making the entire volume of solution with fresh 35 PPT solution. The conditioning system was designed explicitly to store large full-scale specimens, as seen in Figure 2a. Two treatment tanks, one storing each type of RC specimens fed directly into a divided storage tank. Each part of the divided tank accommodated the heated solution from one of the conditioning tanks during the drying cycles with the aim of mitigating cross-contamination from corrosion products and other potential leaching products or sediments.

Material Testing Protocol & Instrumentation

The columns were tested in an 8 MN capacity servo-controlled self-reacting frame at the University of Toronto's Structural Testing Facility using a 10 MN capacity jack (Figure 2b). To ensure uniform concentric loading, Hydrostone gypsum cement was used to square off both ends of the columns to the self-reacting frame. Furthermore, the columns were first loaded to 200kN and then unloaded to make sure that the loading was concentric by comparing deformation readings from around the column. The actual test was performed at a deformation rate of 0.006 – 0.008 mm/s in the elastic region, which was increased to 0.008 – 0.01 mm/s in the post-peak range. The tests were performed to complete failure, i.e., residual load readings were near or close to zero. Each column had 5 longitudinal bar strain gauges, and 5 spiral bar strain gauges, where three of each were placed near the middle of the testing zone to triangulate the bar strain. Lastly, two sets of 4 linear variable displacement transformers (LVDTs) were used as external instrumentations, at gauge lengths of 2.2d and 1.15d, respectively. These LVDTs were placed around the column at equal spacing to gather the average concrete strain during the test. All bar tests were completed to complete rupture using the MTS the 1000 kN capacity machine with attached clip gauges. The concrete cylinders were tested using the MTS 4500 kN stiff frame with two LVDTs on each side, up to 50% of the peak load on the descending branch of the response curve.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Reinforcement Tensile Tests

The results of tension coupon tests are presented in Figure 4. They are expressed as ratios of the conditioned material property of interest at a specific conditioning time to the ambient material properties. The properties of interest at this stage of the study are tensile strength retention (TSR) and elastic modulus retention (EMR). Strength and modulus properties are based on original bar areas. In general, fiber rupture caused the failure of the GFRP bars, where in some cases complete bar ruptures occurred and in others partial amounts of fibers ruptured on the edge of the bars (Figure 5c). This difference is typically attributed to failure conditions (test to full load loss or partial load loss). No discernible change in failure type was observed across different conditioning periods. Steel bar tests showed uniform successive failure modes throughout the conditioning period including yielding, strain hardening and necking (Figure 5b). The GFRP bars showed only minimal degradation after conditioning cycles, such as slight staining from dissolved molecules and sediments in the solution. In contrast, the steel bars clearly exhibited corrosion after exposure (Figure 5a).

a) Tensile Strength Retention (TSR) of GFRP Bars

b) Elastic Modulus Retention (EMR) of GFRP Bars

c) Tensile Load Retention (TLR) of Steel Bars

d) Elastic Modulus Retention (EMR) of Steel Bars

Figure 4: Results of Rebar Tension Tests Before and After Conditioning

a) Steel Bars After 17 Conditioning Cycles

b) Steel Bars - Post Test

c) GFRP Bars - Post Test

Figure 5: Bar Specimen Samples

Effect of Exposure Time on Reinforcement Strength and Stiffness

In general, the effect of conditioning time was well pronounced on the ultimate and yield properties of both steel and GFRP bars. For GFRP bars, the impact was less pronounced for #2 bars, with TSR of 95.4 %, 93.9 % and 98.1 %, while it was more pronounced for #4 bars, with TSR of 93.4 %, 94.6 % and 92.8 % for conditioning times of 17, 34 and 52 weeks, respectively. On the other hand, steel bar tests showed ultimate load retentions of 91.2 %, 64.3 %, 53.5% for D6 steel, and 97.6 %, 85.9 %, 78.8% for US#4 steel, after exposure times of 17, 34 and 52 weeks, respectively. Steel bars rapidly degraded because of the corrosion mechanism, which leads to losses in cross-sectional area, resulting

in a reduced load-carrying capacity. Comparing US#4 steel bars and #4 GFRP bars, it is observed that GFRP's predicted diffusion degrading process is significantly less. Moreover, the impact of corrosion is more pronounced for smaller diameter bars, as a unit thickness of corrosion has a larger impact on smaller areas. This explains why D6 steel showed lower load retention compared to US#4 steel. The smaller, #2, GFRP bars on the other hand retained higher tensile strength after 52 weeks, which may be attributed to the surface finish of this type which visually appeared to be less porous.

With regard to elastic modulus retention, there is little to no change in the properties of GFRP bars. After 52 weeks, GFRP #2 and #3 bars showed EMR of 99.9 % and 98.6%, respectively. This is a marginal change considering the distribution of EMR over the entire 52-week exposure period. The variability of EMR for steel bars over the exposure period (87.4%, 98.7 % and 82.1 % at 17, 34 and 52 weeks, respectively) may be caused by the adverse effects of conditioning and/or the error in strain measurement. The clip gauge is applied on a layer of tape wrapped around the bar (to preserve the gauge) and may have overestimated the deformations as a result of slipping along the corroded surface of the bar.

Effect of Concrete Prisms

The effect of exposure on the behaviour of GFRP bars embedded in concrete prisms is well pronounced as shown in Figure 4a. The bars were tested in tension after the surrounding concrete was removed. The impact of long-term exposure (52 weeks) shows TSR of 77.5 % and 87.6 % for #2 and #4 GFRP bars, respectively. These are 21 % and 5.6 % smaller than their pure-bar counterparts. The high alkaline solution found in the pore water of the embedded concrete can be attributed to this larger reduction in load-carrying capacity. It is shown that GFRP bars exposed to high alkaline solutions either directly, from simulated concrete pore water solutions or embedded concrete conditions can degrade up to 24 % after long-term exposure to alkaline solutions with PH values varying from 12 to 13.6 for temperatures in the range 26°C -53°C (D'Antino et al. 2018). These results provide insights into how the bars will degrade in the conditioned RC columns, as the prisms with embedded bars were constructed to represent the actual designed cover for the bars to the exterior face of the columns. Lastly, the EMR of both #2 and #3 GFRP bars was found to be 96.4 % 97.4 % after 52 weeks. These are 3.5 % and 1.2 % smaller than their bare-bar counterparts while being 3.5 % and 3.1% smaller than the results at 17 weeks. Therefore, a slight downward trend in EMR degradation over time is seen for bars embedded in concrete.

Tests on Columns under Monotonic Compression

Table 5 summarizes the test results of all the column specimens, providing key observations such as axial compressive load, strains in reinforcing bars, concrete strains, and failure modes. Among the four columns described in Table 5, two (SG_C_52 and SS_C_52) were subjected to a conditioning period of 52 weeks, while the other two were kept under ambient laboratory conditions. Discussion on test results is provided in the following sections.

Table 5: Column Experimental Results

Column ID	First Peak		Second Peak		Termination Point				μ	Failure Type (Progressive)
	P_1 [kN]	ϵ_{1c} [$\mu\text{m}/\text{km}$]	P_2 [kN]	ϵ_{2c} [$\mu\text{m}/\text{km}$]	P_3 [kN]	ϵ_{3c} [$\mu\text{m}/\text{km}$]	ϵ_{3l} [$\mu\text{m}/\text{km}$]	ϵ_{3t} [$\mu\text{m}/\text{km}$]		
SG_A_52	1060.3	3544	1134.9	14015	782.3	16907	10627	16511	8.5	SR – LBC – CC
SG_C_52	1020.9	2140	983.0	10669	826.5	12085	12319	6821	8.5	SR – LBC – CC
SS_A_52	1275.1	4106	1326.7	10685	980.6	21083	50996	3957	9.6	LBB – SR – CC
SS_C_52	1194.1	2535	1228.7	4539	819.2	16051	15333	-	8.9	LBB – SR – CC

P_1 = Load at point of interest ϵ_{1c} = concrete strain at load point of interest; ϵ_1 = longitudinal rebar average strain; ϵ_t = spiral/transverse rebar strain; SR = spiral rupture; LBC = long. bar crushing; LBB = long. bar buckling; CC = concrete cone failure; μ = ductility, calculated as concrete strain at P_1 on secant line through $0.85P_1$ divided by strain at termination point (ϵ_{3c})

Discussion of Test Results

Control columns' behaviour

Both the GFRP-reinforced and steel-reinforced control columns were subjected to monotonically increasing compressive loads. Figure 6a illustrates the overall behaviour of the control specimens with

solid curves representing the relationship between axial load and axial strains that can be divided into four phases.

The first phase extends from the beginning of the test until the first peak point (denoted as P1 in Figure 6a), which indicates the onset of cover spalling. The first peak was observed at 1060.3 kN and 1275.1 kN for the SG_A_52 and SS_A_52 column specimens, respectively. It is worth noting that the initial stiffness of both GFRP and steel-reinforced columns' curves was nearly the same, as the behaviour was primarily influenced by the concrete prior to cover spalling.

The second phase, occurring between point P1 and point M on the curves shown in Figure 6a, represents the behaviour during the spalling of concrete and is relatively short. A visible decrease in load for both columns was observed after the first peak. In this phase, cracks were initiated in the concrete cover, leading to gradual spalling and a reduction in the load-resisting cross-sectional area, resulting in strength degradation from P1 to M. This phase concluded with the activation of passive confinement, indicated by significant strain increase in the transverse reinforcements after point M. The load continued to rise again as the test progressed due to the confinement provided by the transverse reinforcement until the second peak (P2) was reached at 1134.9 kN and 1326.7 kN for the SG_A_52 and SS_A_52 specimens, respectively. Notably, the increase in load and axial strain after point M was more significant in the GFRP-reinforced column compared to the steel-reinforced column. This can be attributed to the higher tensile strength of the GFRP spirals. This phase is mainly governed by the transverse reinforcement and the material of the longitudinal bars, culminating at point P2.

After the second peak (P2), the final phase of the overall column behaviour commenced, leading to the ultimate failure of the column. This phase involved a combination of spontaneous failures. Upon close observation, it was determined that in the GFRP-reinforced columns, failure after the second peak was initiated by partial/full spiral bar rupture, followed by longitudinal bar crushing, and ultimately resulted in the crushing of the core concrete in a cone shape, as depicted in Figure 6(b). Similarly, the failure in the steel-reinforced columns was initiated by longitudinal bar buckling, followed by spiral rupture, and ultimately failed due to core concrete crushing. The columns, after the second peak P2, could no longer withstand additional loads, resulting in a gradual drop in load values as failures occurred and ultimately leading to column failure at point 'Pr'. Table 5 summarizes these significant test results, and the progressive failures are also summarized in the last column of Table 5.

a) Axial Load-Strain Profile of Columns

b) Columns in Failed State

Figure 6: Column Test Results

Effect of Exposure on Column Response

Figure 6a also illustrates the axial load-axial strain curves of the conditioned specimens (SG_C_52 and SS_C_52), represented by dashed lines. These conditioned specimens exhibited a slightly stiffer behaviour initially, which can be attributed to the increased strength properties of the concrete resulting from the conditioning process, as summarized in Table 3. However, a consistent reduction in axial strain and load values was observed for the conditioned specimens, corresponding to the first and second peaks, as depicted in Figure 6a. This decline indicates the expected degradation of the reinforcing materials in both the GFRP- and steel-reinforced columns due to the effects of the wet/dry cycles.

As previously discussed, the onset of phase 2 (point 'P1') and the culmination of phase 3 (point 'P2') involve the transition from concrete cover spalling to the activation of passive confinement provided by the transverse reinforcement. The confinement offered by the transverse reinforcement led to increased load values and a significant rise in axial strains or ductility of the columns from points P1 to P2. Notably, the strain at point P2 for the conditioned GFRP-reinforced column was found to be 10.5 times higher than the strain at point P1. This increase in strains from P1 to P2 was due to the confinement provided by the GFRP transverse reinforcement. This increase was approximately 13.2 times for the ambient GFRP-reinforced control column. Therefore, a slight reduction in ductility is caused in the GFRP-reinforced column because of conditioning. In contrast, the ratio of strains at P1 to P2 was approximately 8.4 and 3.8 for the ambient and conditioned steel-reinforced columns, respectively. It is evident that conditioning diminished ductility and the energy-absorbing capacity of the steel column substantially more compared to the GFRP-reinforced column. This finding aligns with the visual observations made after the test, which indicated significant corrosion-induced damage to the steel reinforcing bars compared to the GFRP bars. These observations are also consistent with the degradation of material properties highlighted in Figure 4, suggesting that the steel bars experienced more deterioration due to the conditioning process.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Results from 4 RC column tests, 53 GFRP coupon tests, 25 steel coupon tests and 15-cylinder tests are presented to investigate the impact of a simulated and accelerated marine environment using wet/dry cycles. Based on the experimental results, the following concluding remarks can be made:

- Bare bar tests showed the GFRP bars to be more durable than the steel bars after 52 weeks of conditioning. The GFRP bars embedded in concrete prisms degraded more than bare bar specimens but still had better durability than steel rebar.
- Conditioning of the column specimens for 52 weeks results in significant reduction in responses along the load axis in both types of columns.
- The confinement offered by the transverse reinforcement played a significant role in increasing ductility beyond the first peak. The ductility of GFRP-reinforced columns remained relatively unchanged because of conditioning, while a substantial decrease was observed in the steel-reinforced columns.
- This study provides insights into the comparative durability of GFRP and steel RC in simulated marine conditions. It contributes to an understanding of the performance of GFRP bars as a corrosion-resistant alternative to steel reinforcement in such environments. Further research is underway to investigate additional aspects of GFRP and steel RC durability in marine environments.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.